
KETU - The Beheaded, The Explosive, The Karmic: A Perspective

Kunal Roy

Assistant Professor, Department of English Language and Communication

George Group of Colleges, Kolkata

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ABSTRACT

Saturn and Mars are known as the malefic planets in the realm of cosmos. Like Rahu, Ketu renders results on the basis of our deeds. In Vedic astrology, Ketu is the South node of the Moon. Ketu is considered the shadow of Mars. Both Rahu and Ketu are shadow planets. They are invisible in the house of the solar system. Yet they play a very significant role to ensure a state of equilibrium in the universe. Though beheaded, Ketu has a strong impact upon human life. Ketu helps to discover a new journey from core materialism to absolute spiritualism. The present paper showcases the resources rooted in mythology, the astrological views, the various Kalsarpa dosas. Kal (Rahu), Sarpa (Ketu) and finally the different houses, combinations, zodiac signs, and ascendants. 'KARMA' governs the whole system of our existence. A broader approach to the entire subject, ranging from the position to conjunction to transition and finally the remedial measures. Indeed, the present research will gradually unfold the mysterious nature of Ketu.

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Introduction

The birth of Ketu is found in the spheres of mythology. The Samudra Manthan or churning of the milk ocean was conducted by the Devas and the Asuras to obtain the elixir. However, there was a confused struggle between the Devas and the Asuras. To settle the dispute, Lord Vishnu took the incarnation of

Mohini, the most elegant maiden in the whole universe. She appeared before them and expressed her desire to distribute the nectar between them. She sang, danced and created an overwhelming ambiance, beyond comprehension. Amidst this, Swarbhanu, one of the demons, disguised himself and mingled with the clan of Devas. This manipulation miserably flunked as the sun and the moon recognized him and screamed aloud. Understanding the seriousness of the situation, Mohini transformed herself into Lord Vishnu and instructed his divine discus to behead Swarbhanu. But the nectar managed to reach down his throat and the torso was left aside. This head came to be known as 'Rahu' and the torso came to be known as 'Ketu'. With the flowing of time, their importance is realized in Vedic astrology and undoubtedly their impact too on human life and destiny. Unlike Rahu, Ketu performs its role in material detachment, spiritual attachment, and the awakening of true wisdom. Ketu lays much emphasis on innate transformation for the true liberation of the soul. It is to be noted that Rahu (the umbra) and Ketu (the penumbra) always form a 180-degree axis, encompassing the spheres of life's direction, emotive fights, growth, decline, and ultimate spiritual bliss. This paper attempts to delve deep into the roles performed by Ketu in all the twelve houses. The study provides a deep insight into the phases of Dasha, Antardasha, Protantyar Dasha, and how proper guidance, path, philosophy, hard work, and discipline aid individuals to tide over the immense challenges posed by Ketu, which believes in living a life of detachment and spiritual contentment.

The Objectives of Study

i. To examine and understand the origins of Ketu as found in various auspicious holy texts. ii. To analyze the birth of Ketu after the Samudra Manthan (The Churning of the Milk Ocean). iii. To examine and evaluate Ketu's unparalleled influence on each and every aspect of human life like love, marriage, studies, career, mental conflicts, detachment, attachment, and innate evolution. iv. To examine and elucidate the psychological and karmic influences. v. To examine and review Ketu's influence on the mundane and global scenario.

The Scope of Study

The present paper manages to provide a deep knowledge on the function played by Ketu in the spheres of Karma and Spiritual attachment. However, the scope primarily encompasses a wide range of aspects, ranging from the mythological domain to the astrological vision to the karmic implications to the socio-global influences, supported by a handful of remedial measures which may vary from individual to individual.

The Relevance of Study

Ketu is the penumbral segment of a shadow. Its role is mysterious and often beats the conventional rhythm of human comprehension. Ketu has no "dristi" and therefore this south node of the moon deserves a special analysis of karma, material detachment, and spiritual evolvment. However, the relevance of this particular study is rooted in its placement in one's natal chart, paving the path for challenges, events, victory, and vanquish. Moreover, transits, dasha, mahadasa, antardasha bring forth psychological changes, behavioral patterns, karmic and spiritual significance, social changes, global reflections, and above all, practical moves.

The Methodology of Study

1. Research Design: The study meticulously follows a descriptive and analytical research-model focusing on mythology, astrology, and psychology.
2. Data Collection Methods: a) An in-depth study of individual natal charts with a specific focus on the placement of Ketu and infer its soulful impact on the personal and professional fronts. b) Secondary Sources: Vedic texts and Classical texts: i) Brihat Parashara Hora Shastra, classical works discussing the impact of Ketu. ii) Jataka Parijata and Phaladeepika - discussing the effects of Ketu. iii) Astrological journals and Research Papers - Contemporary influence and interpretation of Ketu. c) Psychological Opinion: Ketu's link with material detachment, spiritual attachment, mental stress, and disorders.

The Primary Characteristics of Ketu

Ketu is exalted in Sagittarius, the house of Jupiter. It is debilitated in Gemini, the house of Mercury. Ketu also provides good results in Pisces, the house of Jupiter. Ketu forms a 180-degree axis with Rahu that reveals an individual's past actions, the present problems, challenges, and the future prospects. Let us have a look at the placement of Ketu in various houses of a natal chart and the eventual results:

Ketu in the first house: an indifferent personality, spiritual inclination, strong identity crisis. Ketu in the second house: speech problem, family issues, detached from money and wealth. Ketu in the third house: intrepid, strong intuitive connection and strained bonds with siblings. Ketu in the fourth house: separated from mother or motherly figure, home, introvert nature and spiritual growth. Ketu in the fifth house: mystic power, past life skills and spiritual calmness. Ketu in the sixth house: hidden enemies, unexplored, mysterious health hazards and love for loneliness. Ketu in the seventh house: delayed marriage, marital issues, sacrifice in relationships. Ketu in the eighth house: love for learning occult science, radical transformation, life span. Ketu in the ninth house: ups and downs in the favor of luck,

spiritual guide, and a digression from orthodoxy. Ketu in the tenth house: disruption in career graph, innate discontent, karmic profession. Ketu in the eleventh house: weird friendships, disinterest in making gains, strong spiritual networks and at times a very good flow of money. Ketu in the twelfth house: salvation, isolation and renunciation.

The Probable Results of Ketu's combination with other planets

Ketu and Sun: Feeble/absent father or fatherly figure, Ego conflicts, identity crisis, spiritual interest through pains and sufferings, loss of fame or name in early life, revival in the later period of life and self-realization.

Ketu and Moon: Mental restlessness, anxiety, issues with mother and women, good intuition, love for mysticism and seclusion.

Ketu and Mars: Severe aggression, confusion, blood issues, head injuries, accidents, surgical issues, steadiness towards the accomplishment of goal.

Ketu and Mercury: Learning and Speech difficulties in children, highly analytical and philosophical, skilled writer, researcher and nervousness.

Ketu and Jupiter: Guru's connection in the past life, redefining or rejecting the concept of religion, self-guided wisdom, confusion, knowledge, and illusion.

Ketu and Venus: Crack in relationships, detachment from sensual pleasures, maverick or secret love life, inclination for art and mystical themes.

Ketu and Saturn: Enhancing solitude, procrastination, detachment from worldly affairs, interest in occult science, spiritual expansion through simplicity.

It is to be noted that the placement of Rahu and Ketu in a perfect straight line ensures intense innate conflict, abrupt rise and fall of status, experiences of both extremes of life, lofty spiritual and mental complexity, radical transformation, mystical evolution.

Kalsarpa Dosa

It is interesting to note that 'Kalsarpa Dosa' occurs when all the planets come on one side of the natal chart with Rahu, Ketu, and Jupiter. In other words, when the five respective houses of a natal chart are empty. However, the individuals who have this particular dosa are very talented, but the talent doesn't get an exposure in the accepted sense of the term. The 'Dosa' gradually reduces its impact after thirty-five years of an individual. Depending on the exact placement, twelve types of Kalsarpa Dosas are formed, influencing an individual's life.

1. 'Ananta KalSarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the first house and Ketu is in the seventh house. The results include self-identity crisis, delayed or no marriages, strained bonds, and health problems.
2. 'Kulik Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the second house and Ketu is in the eighth house. The results include financial crunch, household conflicts, sudden accidents and obviously health hazards.
3. 'Vasukhi Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the third house and Ketu is in the ninth house. The results include a break in education, perturbed with siblings and father, struggle in luck and higher studies.
4. 'Shankpal Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the fourth house and Ketu is in the tenth house. The results include problems related to property (movable and immovable), mother's health, instability in career or profession and spoil of public image.
5. 'Padma Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the fifth house and Ketu is in the eleventh house. The results include issues with child birth, intelligence, romance, mental instability and failure in speculation.
6. 'Mahapadma Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the sixth house and Ketu is in the twelfth house. The results include debts, enemies, health hazards, legal problems and salvation.
7. 'Takshak Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu is the seventh house and Ketu is in the first house. The results include marital problems, identity crisis and public image issues.
8. 'Karkotak Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the eighth house and Ketu is in the first house. The results include sudden events, ancestral property issues and speculation set back.
9. 'Shanknaad Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the ninth house and Ketu is in the third house. The results include obstacles in fortune, disturbance in fatherly relation and higher education.
10. 'Patak Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the tenth house and Ketu is in the fourth house. The results include career issues, public respect and mother's health.
11. 'Vishadhar Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the eleventh house and Ketu is in the fifth house. The results include delayed success, losses through friends and childhood problems.
12. 'Sheshnag Kalsarpa Dosa' is formed when Rahu sits in the twelfth house and Ketu is in the sixth house. The results include sudden losses, foreign settlement, struggles and spiritual dilemmas. On the other hand, there are a handful of astrologers who opine that there is nothing

called as 'Kalsarpa Dosa'. However, the ancient texts have often referred to this sheer problem and the typical ways involved to tide over this problem.

Rahu - Ketu Cosmic Transition from One Zodiac to another Zodiac

Rahu and Ketu always sit opposite to one another in a natal chart. Every eighteen months they transit from one house to another. This particular trait brings about abrupt changes, spiritual sublimity and obvious endings.

Certain Remedial measures

To pacify Ketu, certain remedial measures can be taken. However, one has to remember that such steps will only work if one does good Karma in every sphere. a) Chanting the holy mantra of Ketu. b) Feeding white dogs. c) Worship of Lord Ganesha or Kalbhairav. d) Wearing cat's eye in the little finger of the right hand. e) Authentic penance to mature a sense of worldly detachment.

Conclusion

Although Ketu is said to be very calm and composed, yet it renders sudden results like a volcanic eruption. The Mahadasha of Ketu is of seven years. Ketu makes us realize the abundance hidden in truth and sacrifice. A shift from the material or make-believe world. In a world where illusion, greed, and materialism rule the roost, Ketu reveals the path of spiritual revolution, true wisdom, and moksha (salvation). Unraveling the mystery of Ketu may not be a part of finite human comprehension. But the blessings are always there for the true awakening of the soul.

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